

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

What does ploughing do?

A mouldboard plough was a revolutionary technology when it was introduced in the 18th century. It allowed turning the soil over to a deep depth, converting grasslands to arable fields rapidly and even with the limited amount of traction power available then from horses. The basic design has remained the same, although modern tractor pulled ploughs can work deeper and faster than the horse-drawn equivalents.

A plough cuts the soil both vertically (30-50 cm spacing) and horizontally (10-35 cm depth) and then turns the cut block over to bury the soil surface. Skimmers are added to ensure that all the residue is turned over to the ploughing depth. The lifting and turning also creates fractures, which allow crumbling the soil with further tillage implements into a seedbed.

Ploughing has three problems for managing soil health: it kills soil organisms, it leaves the soil bare and it compacts the subsoil.

The intensive and deep working of the soil kills organisms such as earthworms and beetles and the following drying leaves a hostile environment for earthworms. Burial of crop residue leaves the soil bare, which heats it up and leaves it unprotected against rain erosion. This is emphasized by burying the surface soil with high aggregate stability and digging up subsoil which has low aggregate stability. Finally, ploughing can create a plough-pan, a compacted layer below the plowing depth. The plough-pan is created by both the tractor tyre running in the furrow and by the plough share running on the subsoil and supporting the lifted soil.

In spite of the problems, in some cases ploughing may be necessary if the soil surface has become problematic for farming due to weeds, plant diseases or excess nutrients.

1. A heavy plough moves almost all of the weight of the tractor to the rear axle.

KEYWORDS

Tillage, ploughing, soil structure, soil functions

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